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“A MOTHER’S PAIN”

She wishes to be a perfect Mom, but she failed.
She got married at a perfect age, a stable job, and a very promising career ahead.
She got three kids a boy and two beautiful girls.
She loved them in all fair.

Time passes by these children are growing tall.
Mom’s career becomes time demanding almost all.
She thought all is smooth and well,
Until she discovered what her children feel.

Time for kids is rare,
The thought of giving them money is fair.
She realized doing so made them stay away,
And made the children live on their own way.

The thought of doing all these things are for the kids,
But it made her realized she failed.
A mother’s pain is real,
When that dreams for you kids failed.